

PHILOLOGY

INTERNET JOURNALISM AS AN IDEAL FREE AND OPERATIVE MEANS OF INFORMATION

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Abstract

Internet journalism, also called as digital journalism, cyber journalism or netizen Journalism, is defined as the reporting of facts when produced and distributed via the Internet. In other words, it's a contemporary form of journalism where editorial content is distributed via the internet compared to publishing it via print or broadcast. Digital Journalism made an entrance to the scene since 1990s and yes that's when the Internet made its entrance as well. Many large journalist media such as newspapers and television networks opened their own websites to feed the needs of their audience with additional material to that the exhibited either on paper or on TV.

What constitutes as online journalism has been debated by scholars; however, what they have agreed on is the fact that a product that is news and features the current scene, either presented solely or in combination with other tools including text, audio, video or other interactive forms like storytelling, and distributed through digital media technology is a form of digital journalism.

This leads us to the next step... The article analyzes the features that make online journalism special, its difference from traditional journalism, and summarizes the results.

Keywords: internet journalism, Wikipedia, worldwide, user content, social media, mass media, AI.

Through the Internet, which is considered the biggest phenomenon of the 21st century, a fundamental change is observed in the information environment and in the field of journalism. Professor Russell Newman, an expert on media technologies, characterizes these changes as follows:

- changed the essence of geographical distance;
- created a great progress in the development of communication;
- created conditions for increasing the speed of communication;
- increased the possibilities of interactive communication;
- played a role in combining previously separate and unrelated forms of communication.(1)

Although interactivity is considered one of the main factors in the functioning of new media, individual media samples have different degrees of interactivity. Tony Feldman in his book "Introduction to Electronic Media" notes that the number of digital satellite televisions, which are considered new media technologies, is increasing. But from the point of view of meeting the demand of the viewers, they cannot demonstrate interactivity. This means that interactivity, unlike digitality, is by no means characteristic of all new media technologies. (2)

The most used mobile applications in the messaging service are those with live streaming capabilities. Live communication - Wechat, Facebook, WhatsApp, Messenger, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat and other such applications - is spreading more rapidly in recent times. Facebook currently has over three billion monthly active users. Meta Platforms owns four of the largest social media platforms with one billion monthly active users each: Facebook (main platform), WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger and Instagram. Countries with the highest profile social platforms USA and

China Most of the high-profile social networks with billions of users come from the USA, but services such as the Chinese social networks WeChat, QQ or the video sharing app Douyin also attract the main attention in their regions due to local context and content. Douyin's popularity led to the launch of an international version of a small software platform called TikTok, which currently ranks 6th in the ranking of social networks with 1.5 billion users. (3)

Although traditional television, radio, newspapers still exist, interactivity, promptness, pluralism, etc. it is obvious that it will lose to online media. According to the experts' analysis, compared to Web 1.0, the Web 2.0, the Web 3.0 model allows users not only to comment on the created content, but also to create new content within the topic and upload photos.

The modern development of information technologies has also created a new model of traditional television and radio - Internet television and Internet radio. Internet television and radio is considered as an electronic information medium that is spread by hundreds of thousands and millions of people through the global network and the whole planet becomes its consumer. Today, newspapers, radio, television and modern mass media in the world play the role of a mirror of the people and act as a bridge between the government and society. For example, any important decision made by the government needs to be communicated to citizens in a way they can understand. The media should fulfill this mission.

New media also play an important role in shaping public opinion. It is clear that in the modern era, the mass media (mass media) act as an educational tool in understanding the nature of socio-political and socio-economic events, learning and defending rights and freedoms, getting acquainted with various problems and finding ways to solve them.

At a time when news stories can be written (or recorded), and distributed worldwide in a matter of minutes, saying the digital age has transformed journalism is an understatement. (4)

Technology has permanently changed the way news is created, presented, and consumed. While there's more easily accessible content than ever before, many would argue that the overall quality of journalism has declined. Others love the way it's led to the adoption of a variety of different news sources and platforms.

News reporting has always been deadline driven, but the speed of today's newsgathering leaves old-school journalism in the dust. However remarkable the tech tools, each story needs a critical and experienced eye before publication, and this step is often rushed or even skipped, leading to errors and inaccuracies. Funding for long-term, investigative pieces has also been slashed at TV news stations and newspapers, leading to a significant dearth of in-depth coverage. In the mad race to grab the attention of the world's eyeballs, some of the principles of journalism are brushed aside.

But the digital age has also democratized journalistic processes, leading to a new era where citizens with the desire and ability can report on stories themselves through a variety of tools and platforms. Now the power has shifted—we can all decide what's newsworthy or not.

Whether you see them as good or bad the changes are here, and we must adapt. Things are only getting more bizarre with the advent of sophisticated AI tools capable of writing complete articles—a topic we'll leave for another discussion.

There are several aspects that distinguish new media from traditional media. The emergence of new media creates a fundamental change in the activities of mass media representatives. The wide spread of social networks is observed with drastic changes in the media industry. Due to technological possibilities, the term "personal media" has appeared as an alternative to the concept of "mass media".

The main differences between traditional and new media are:

- new media are more flexible than traditional media;
- new media is open, traditional media is closed;
- new media addresses the users, while traditional media addresses the public;
- texts are short in new media and long in traditional media;
- new media conveys the picture, traditional media text;
- new media is active, traditional media is passive.

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